

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

The use of microbial biofertilizers can enhance soil quality, increase melon yield, and reduce the demand for chemical fertilizers.

The Mediterranean region faces serious challenges in the provision of essential resources such as energy, water, and soil due to low levels of soil organic carbon and land degradation. Furthermore, climate change is increasing the risk of desertification and land degradation in Mediterranean Europe, which are intensified by agricultural practices and the excessive use of conventional fertilizers. Therefore, there is a strong need for urgent changes in management practices. The study aims to assess the potential of microorganisms as a partial replacement for mineral fertilization in soil health and performance in a melon crop. The study assessed soil biochemical indicators related to nitrogen cycle enzymatic activities, pesticide presence and decomposition, cellulose digestion by microorganisms, and plant

organic matter degradation. Four treatments were applied: a) F100 (conventional fertilization); b) BA+FU (nutrient solubilizing bacteria and fungi + 50% of fertilization reduction); c) BA (nutrient solubilizing bacteria + 50% of fertilization reduction); d) F50 (only 50% of fertilization reduction). The results showed that using commercial products of N-fixing and nutrient-solubilizing bacteria and fungi, along with reducing chemical fertilizer input, could improve plant growth, melon fruit weight, and Brix degrees. The study suggests this agricultural practice could be a sustainable technique for improving crop yield and profitability. The combined effect of microbial biofertilizers and mineral fertilizers performed better than chemical fertilizers alone.

1. Melon plantation in Mediterranean South region (Spain).

KEYWORDS

Biofertilizers, chemical fertilizers, melon crop, soil quality, crop yield.

AUTHORSHIP

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